

4. S. MUKHERJEE, *Proc. 60th Sess. Indian Sci. Cong., 1973, Part III*, 69.
5. S. MUKHERJEE, *Proc. 61st Sess. Indian Sci. Cong., 1974, Part III*, 77.
6. P. K. PARIJA and S. K. MAJUMDAR, *Analyt. Chim. Acta*, 1975, **74**, 197.
7. P. K. PARIJA and S. K. MAJUMDAR, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1975, **274**, 127.
8. P. K. PARIJA and S. K. MAJUMDAR, *Indian J. Chem.* 1975, **13**, 743.

Estimation of linuron residues in some fodder crops and soils*

R. K. GUPTA and T. R. DUTTA
Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute,
Jhansi-284001

*Manuscript received 11 September 1975, accepted 28
January 1976*

LINURON (N-3,4-dichlorophenyl-N'-methoxy-N'-methyl urea) has been successfully used as a selective herbicide for the control of many annual grasses and broadleaf weeds in a variety of fodder and food crops enabling higher agricultural productivity. Estimation of herbicide residues in treated crops and soils becomes imperative to ensure that these, if present are well within the prescribed tolerance and are non-hazardous either to consumer or to subsequent crop. Methods for residues determination reported by Lowen and Baker¹; Bleidner² and Bleidner³ *et al* consisted of hydrolytic-decomposition of linuron and quantitative estimation of the liberated N, O-dimethyl hydroxyl amine and 3,4-dichloroaniline respectively. Kirkland⁴ described a gas chromatographic technique using flame ionization detector. In the present communication, we describe a simple, accurate and reproducible colorimetric method for the extraction and determination of linuron residues in sunflower, oats, soyabean fodders, wheat grains and straws and soils. The method consists of quantitative conversion of linuron to 3,4-dichloroaniline which, on diazotization with nitrous acid and coupling with alkaline β -naphthol solution forms a red dye. The absorbance of the dye dissolved in methanol is measured at 540 nm in a photoelectric colorimeter against methanol (40%) as blank. The sampling, extraction, hydrolysis, purification, chromatographic clean-up procedures have been discussed.

Experimental

Standard curve: Calibration curve was prepared in terms of 3,4-dichloroaniline (DCA). A solution of DCA in 0.1N hydrochloric acid (0.01 mg DCA per ml) was used. 0.4, 0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2.0 and 2.4 ml DCA solutions were taken in six test tubes and the volume in each was made to 2.4 ml by adding requisite quantity of hydrochloric acid (0.1 N). 0.5 ml sodium nitrite solution (1.4%) was added to each tube and the reaction completed in ten minutes.

Excess of sodium nitrite was destroyed by the addition of 0.5 ml ammonium sulphamate solution (8%). After 5 min 1 ml β -naphthol solution (100 mg dissolved in 100 ml of 2% potassium hydroxide) was added and allowed to stand for 10 min. The contents of the test tubes were thoroughly mixed after addition of each reagent. Finally 2 ml methanol was added which dissolved the dye producing a transparent solution. The absorbance was measured at 540 nm against methanol (40%) as blank. The concentration of DCA was plotted against optical density and the amount of herbicide calculated (0.01 mg DCA = 0.0154 mg linuron).

Sampling and extraction: Freshly harvested plant samples (200–500 g) were made homogeneous to a fine pulp in a blender, mixed with celite (15–20 g) and transferred to a Soxhlet extractor with acetone. The extraction was continued for 4 hr. Acetone was distilled at diminished pressure and the extractive was refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide (20%; 100 ml) for 3 hr. The contents were allowed to cool to room temperature and made acidic (pH 2) with hydrochloric acid. Alcohol was distilled off and the hydrolysate transferred to a 500 ml separating funnel and made alkaline (pH 10) with potassium hydroxide solution (10%). It was extracted with three successive 200 ml portions of ether. The ether extract was washed free of alkali with distilled water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and carefully concentrated to about 50 ml.

Chromatographic clean-up: The coloured interferences were removed from the ether extract by chromatography over a column of neutral alumina Brockmann's grade. The column (40 × 1.5 cm) fitted with the stopcock was prepared by putting a plug of glass wool at the base of the column and alumina was introduced as slurry in a mixture of petroleum ether and ether (1 : 1) taking care that no air bubble could remain in the column. The top of the column was covered with a thin padding of glass wool. The ether extract and its washings were poured over the column which was eluted with a mixture of petroleum ether and ether (1 : 2). The eluate (150 ml) was collected in a separating funnel and extracted with hydrochloric acid (0.1N) thrice in succession (20, 10, 10 ml). The acid extract was taken in a 50 ml volumetric flask. The flask was gently heated on a water bath at 45° for 10 min to drive off the dissolved solvent ether and after cooling made to volume with hydrochloric acid (0.1N). The DCA was estimated colorimetrically as above.

Determination of herbicide in plant and soil samples fortified with known amounts of linuron gave uniform recoveries. The method could be used for estimation of linuron residues in sunflower, oats, soyabean fodders, wheat grains and straws and soils. The lower limit of determination being 1 ppm linuron.

Acknowledgement

Our thanks are due to the Director, Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute, Jhansi for providing the facilities.

* The paper was read at the Annual Convention of Chemists 1974 held at Madurai.

References

1. W. K. LOWEN and H. M. BAKER, *Anal. Chem.*, 1952, 24, 1475.
2. W. E. BLEIDNER, H. M. BAKER, M. LEVITSKY and W. K. LOWEN, *J. Agr. Food Chem.*, 1954, 2, 476.
3. W. E. BLEIDNER, *J. Agr. Food Chem.*, 1954, 2, 682.
4. J. J. KIRKLAND, *Anal. Chem.*, 1962, 34, 428.

Flavone glycosides from the flowers of *Morinda citrifolia*

JAGDAMBA SINGH and R. D. TIWARI

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211002

Manuscript received 15 September 1975 ;

accepted 28 January 1976

FROM the hot ethanolic extract of the flowers of *Morinda citrifolia* two flavone glycosides, (i) acacetin-7-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside and (ii) 5,7-dimethyl apigenin-4'-*O*- β -D(+) galactopyranoside and also an anthraquinone glycoside have been isolated and studied.

The first compound, m.p. 244°-45°, molecular formula $C_{22}H_{12}O_{10}$, when hydrolysed with mineral acid gave acacetin $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ and glucose. The structure of acacetin has been confirmed by analysis colour reactions spectral data and preparation of derivatives. The position of the sugar linkage has been shown to be with 7-hydroxyl group by the study of spectral shift using aluminium chloride¹ and sodium acetate². That glucose is present in the pyranose form has been proved by periodate oxidation and nature of the glycoside linkage as β - has been confirmed by its hydrolysis with emulsin.

The other flavone glycoside m.p. 178°-80° (d), molecular formula $C_{23}H_{24}O_{10}$, on hydrolysis with mineral acid gave an aglycone $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ (m.p. 295°) and galactose. The aglycone has been shown to be 5,7-dimethyl apigenin by analysis, colour reactions spectral data and preparation of derivatives. The position of the sugar linkage has been shown to be with the 4'-hydroxyl group by the study of spectral shifts using ethoxide reagent³. That galactose is in the pyranose form has been established by periodate oxidation and the β -linkage of the glycoside by hydrolysis with emulsin.

The compound acacetin-7-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside is known and has been reported earlier from several plant sources^{4,5}. The other glycoside, 5,7-dimethyl apigenin-4'-*O*- β -D(+) galactopyranoside, has not been reported earlier from any plant source, though another glycoside namely 5,7-dimethyl-4'-*O*- β -D(+) glucopyranoside has been recently reported by Dubey and Mishra⁶ from sugar cane peelings.

The third compound isolated from this plant is an anthraquinone glycoside which is being studied and will be reported later.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of the authors (J.S.).

References

1. R. M. HOROWITZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 6561.
2. L. JURD and R. M. HOROWITZ, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1618.
3. C. G. NORDSTROM and T. SWAIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2764.
4. M. NOGRADI, L. FRANKS and H. WAGNER, *Chem. Ber.*, 1967, 9, 100.
5. P. P. KHVOROST, Fenot'nye Saedin. Ikh. Boil. Funkts., Mater. Vases. Sunp. Ist. 1966, 85.
6. R. C. DUBEY and K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 654.

Mixed ligand complexes of Bis (ethylacetoacetato) Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with nitrogen donors

A. K. JENA and B. K. MOHAPATRA

Department of Chemistry, Ravenshaw College, Cuttack-3

Manuscript received 25 October 1975,

accepted 14 January 1976

β DIKETONES and related compounds which exhibit keto-enol tautomerism react with metal cations to form complexes which behave as Lewis acids and form adducts with Lewis bases. Several such base adducts of β -diketonates of Zn(II) and copper(II) have been reported earlier¹⁻⁵. The complexes of β -keto esters closely resemble those of β -diketonates. Therefore, it was thought worthwhile to study the base adduct formation with ethylacetoacetato complexes and this communication describes eight base adducts of bis(ethylacetoacetato) Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II) with quinoline and isoquinoline.

Experimental

Metal chelates were prepared by reacting ethanolic solution of metal chlorides with ethylacetoacetato in (1 : 2) ratio followed by dropwise addition of sodium acetate solution. The precipitated compounds were filtered under suction, washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in *vacuo*. Bis(ethylacetoacetato) metal(II) was suspended in minimum volume of ethanol and base was added in (1 : 2) ratio and the mixture refluxed till a clear solution was obtained. On keeping the clear solution overnight crystalline compounds separated out.

Metal and nitrogen in the compounds were estimated by standard methods. Conductance was measured in *M*/1000 acetone solution using "Toshniwal's Conductivity Bridge". Infra-red spectra were recorded on Nujol mulls using Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer and electronic spectra in *M*/100 (chloroform base mixture) solution with Hilger Watt Uvispek spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility